

Children, pets and statistical investigation: A sociocritical dialogue

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We describe the theoretical framework, development, and reflection of a master's research. We seek to understand: "What statistical competencies (statistical literacy, statistical reasoning, and statistical thinking) do 6-year-olds in a 1st-grade class of elementary school constitute when conducting a statistical investigation?" The Data production was performed through a set of tasks, developed by the researcher and the children. In this paper we present the investigation context "Mistreatment of the pet dogs". In our analysis, we found that the tasks and the methodology chosen contributed to developing of competencies such as statistical literacy, statistical reasoning, and statistical thinking and allowed the children to reflect on the social justice.

Introduction

This paper presents a statistical investigation about the "Mistreatment of the pet dogs" developed by first-grade students in an elementary school. This paper draws of the master research developed by Mendes (2020), under the supervision of Vilas Bôas in the Professional Postgraduate Master's Degree Programme in Education: Teacher Qualification for Basic Education of the University of Uberaba, Uberlândia, Brazil. The participants were 28 children, aged about 6 years old. The aim of the project was to engage the children in a statistics project, by collecting data, organising them in tables, and displaying them in a graph. The Investigation Context was the types of mistreatments that can be inflicted on pet dogs.

Our aim for the project was to show that statistics education can be focused on social praxis, involving a theme that encompasses real problems and situations from a contextualised perspective, through a reflective and critical investigation. The question of research aimed to identify and understand which statistical competencies (literacy, statistical reasoning, and statistical thinking) do 6-year-olds attending a 1st-grade class of the elementary school develop when conducting a statistical investigation. As a general objective, we chose to investigate the development of statistical competences in this group of children.

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Fundamentals of the theory: Statistics education, the research's theoretical perspective

Whatever the area or object of study of the researcher, he/she may use statistical concepts. Daily newspapers are rich in graphs, indexes, and comparative analyses of all species. In the Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE; Bargagliotti, Franklin, Arnold, Gould, Johnson, Perez, & Spangler, 2007), statistics is described as important in many professional activities such as providing nutritional information and establishing the safety and efficacy of medicines among others. Frankenstein (1987), cited by Borba and Skovsmose (2001), states that the incorrect use of mathematical information leads to discrimination and proposes the use of mathematical problems inserted in social situations as a way to empower students through mathematical tools that will enable them to have a critical view of the world. Given the importance of statistics in everyday life, it can play fulfil the role, outlined by Frankenstein to overcome discrimination and empower students.

Thus, mathematical and statistical data can contribute to important debates in society, which can provide a way of reading of the world. In this way, a broader view of everyday situations, can “become part of the language with which political, technological, and administrative suggestions are presented” (Borba & Skovsmose, 2001, p. 127), and can contribute to social justice, equality, and autonomy.

We believe that engage well-designed statistical projects can fulfil the characteristics of critical education. Our approach to critical statistics education is in alignment with Campos (2017, p. 125), who described the objective of teaching statistics as always needing to be accompanied by the objective of developing students' criticality. This must accompany their engagement in political and social issues, relevant to their democratic citizenship and who fight for social justice in a humanised and non-estranged environment.

Campos et al. (2011) propose that it is crucial to teach in an environment that provides research and reflection on problems related to the students' daily lives. Thus, students are called to take responsibility for the information, understanding and reflecting and then drawing their conclusions about the results obtained. In terms of statistics education, Campos et al. (2011, p. 14), stated that students should “be prepared to raise problems of interest, formulate questions [...], collect data, [...], reflect, discuss and critically analyse the results.” Consequently, Rumsey (2002), Garfield (1998), Chance (2002), and DelMas (2002) argue that students need to gain and make use of three essential statistical competencies: statistical literacy, statistical reasoning, and statistical thinking.

Garfield (2002) sees statistical literacy as the understanding of terminology, symbols, and the skills to interpret graphs and tables. The author also explains that statistical reasoning is related to the way individuals' reason with statistical ideas, that is how statistical information makes sense to them. For Chance (2002), students who developed statistical thinking can think beyond the problem raised; they can seek beyond the information they are offered. For Chance, statistical thinking is an ability to see globally, to understand the process altogether.

Process, Cycle, Phase of a statistical investigation

Lopes (2004) proposes that the investigative perspective should form the basis for the teaching and learning process because students would experience the conception and analysis of data. Lopes highlights five steps that make up the statistical investigation process: Defining the question; Collecting data; Representing data; Interpreting data, and Making decisions. The researcher highlights that, by taking these steps, students are able to build skills that will help them deal with everyday statistical concepts, thus favoring the development of important skills such as: Statistical Literacy, Statistical Reasoning and Statistical Thinking. GAISE (Bargagliotti et al., 2007) names these five steps as Phases of the Statistical Method and classified them into four other stages:

I. Formulate Questions: clarify the problem at hand; formulate one (or more) questions that can be answered with data; II. Collect Data: design a plan to collect appropriate data; employ the plan to collect the data; III. Analyze Data: select appropriate graphical and numerical methods; use these methods to analyze the data; IV. Interpret Results: interpret the analysis; relate the interpretation to the original question. (Bargagliotti et al., 2007, p. 11).

Although those authors address different aspects of a statistical investigation, they seem to converge to the same actions. To carry out a statistical investigation both Lopes (2004) and Bargagliotti et al. (2007) suggest: Formulating questions to be investigated; Elaborating hypotheses; Choosing sample and collection instruments; Collecting data; Interpreting and representing them.

Investigation contexts

Choosing the contexts for statistical investigations comes with its own criteria. For example, Alrø and Skovsmose (2010) wrote, “conducting an investigation means abandoning the comforts of certainty and getting carried away by curiosity” (p. 123).

Campos (2017, p. 113) describes an Investigation Context, as a “set of tasks, which are, first of all, a context of development of knowledge, skills, and, therefore, a space for data production.” As in the landscape of investigation proposed by Alrø and Skovsmose (2010), in the Investigation Contexts, students are responsible for the investigative process. Thus, the research contexts are the means and places in which data production takes place. It is the space where children carry out the search for information to solve, understand and analyse the task propositions.

Methodology: Procedures of the research and analysis

For a better understanding of the research problem, a qualitative investigation was carried out in the participant mode. The research was conducted in the second half of 2019 weekly meetings at the Municipal Elementary School Mario Alves de Araújo Silva¹. The institution is maintained by the Municipality of Uberlandia and administered through the Municipal

¹ The Municipal Department of Education authorized the disclosure of the name of the school for the purpose of publishing the research

Department of Education. Twenty-eight children (aged between 6 and 7 years) attending a 1st-grade class at elementary school participated in the research. We developed our research in four stages: i) bibliographic study; ii) elaborating tasks performed in each phase of the statistical investigation; iii) data production developing the investigation contexts, and iv) search result analysis.

We review the theoretical framework of Statistical Education present in doctoral theses, master's theses, books that discuss Statistical Education, journal of articles and event proceedings in the area of Statistical Education and Mathematics Education.

The data production was carried out with participant observation and the researcher's intervention by proposing a set of tasks, developed in the Investigation Contexts, which were elaborated from the theoretical framework. The themes addressed were: what is my pet; what is the care and mistreatment of the pet dog.

While planning the investigation context and development of tasks in the classroom, we used different resources from the children's environment that allowed them to recognise various kinds of information that involved the statistical investigation. We used different instruments to collect research data: audio and video recordings of the task development and we took field notes.

The data production of the research happened during the realization of the Investigation Context. For the development of the tasks, we offered the children situations, in which they experimented: resolution strategies, dialogued with their colleagues, tested and verified their ideas and communicated their reasoning to the colleagues and the researcher. From the dialogues with the children, we organized different ways to collect, organize and represent data, as the investigation Contexts were developed.

For data analysis of the research, we chose to triangulate the data from the student, the teacher, and the researcher and look at the field diary alongside the audio/video recordings. Throughout the we developed 12 Investigation Contexts, including 28 tasks that were divided into three themes, "What kind of pet do you have?" "Care for the pet dog," and "Mistreatment of the pet dogs." The statistical investigation developed in the first two themes involved the classes at the school, and the third theme went beyond the school walls, involving children's families and friends. The investigation context happened during two weeks, for a total of seven hours, and aimed to promote dialogue and alert children about the mistreatment of pet dogs, stimulate their awareness of the problem and evoke their critical consciousness to this problem, and combine statistical development skills with social justice issues.

The investigation context: "Mistreatment of pet dogs"

In Brazil, every day, we hear about numerous cases of animal abuse, understood as violence and physical disrespect against animals, for example, "abandoning; beating; striking; mutilating; poisoning; keeping trapped in chains permanently; keeping in small and unsanitary places; not sheltering from the sun, rain, and cold; denying them water and food daily; denying veterinary assistance, and others" (Dias, 2000, pp. 156–157).

Guimarães (2019) describes the teaching of statistics as having investigation as its structuring axis, in which autonomous appropriation of knowledge contributes to reflective practices about the world. For this reason, the tasks of this investigation context were proposed in such a way that it would allow children to investigate autonomously and freely. Besides, it favoured the interaction between students and social practices, approaching another field of knowledge, contributing to interdisciplinary learning.

Task 1: Establishing the research theme

According to the requirements for engaging in an investigative task, children must recognise the situation and the challenge involving it. Thus, to ask the question “What kind of mistreatment of pet dogs have you ever seen?”, we created an environment that provided dialogue on the subject. We played two movies/cartoons,² “The Abandoned Dog” and the “Kitbull,” for the children. The objective was show scenes of social injustice to sensitise and enhance the dialogue on the subject in such a way that the subject would emerge more easily and allow children to remember facts already witnessed regarding animal mistreatment.

Task 2: Data collection

Once we established with the students what to investigate, we decided with the group which population would be investigated. The children interviewed five people among their family members and neighbourhood friends. The children were instructed to carry out the following procedures at home: choose five people to answer the survey, tabulate the answers and fill in the table.

The objective was to take outside the school, through a statistical investigation, an alert to a topic of great social injustice: cruelty, chaining, beating, abandoning, not providing help, lack of hygiene, lack of food, dirty place, and tick-infested animals, as shown in Figure 1. As a data collection tool, we used an investigation sheet³ with these variables.

The investigative question choice was: “Which animal mistreatment have you ever seen?” With this question, we contemplate what the BNCC (2017) guides, bringing discussions on topics of social urgency, based on ethical, democratic, sustainable and solidary principles.

Task 3: Data organisation (2 hours)

Each child received a table, Figure 2, made by the researcher to register the data collected. During the explanation of how to execute the activity, we sought to establish a dialogue with the children so that it was possible to make them aware of the importance of organising the data collected with an investigative look at the results. The children collected and tabulated data without the teacher’s or the researcher’s intervention in an individual and autonomous way, which are essential characteristics for the formation of critical citizens.

² The drawings can be found at the following addresses: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AZS5cgybKcI> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rFiZEm0ww8k>

³ Term chosen by the children, since the class associated the word investigation throughout the research as a way to discover something that is not known.

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FICHA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO

NOME DA FÉBDA INVESTIGADA: _____

QUEREMOS INVESTIGAR QUAIS DESES MAUS TRATOS ABAIXO
 VOCE JÁ PRESENÇIOU (PODE MARCAR MAIS DE UMA OPÇÃO)

<input type="checkbox"/> CRUELDADE 		
<input type="checkbox"/> ABANDONAR "Quando abandonamos um animal, somos como quem não quer mais nada." - PAULO COELHO 		
<input type="checkbox"/> FALTA DE ALIMENTAÇÃO 		

Denuncie maus tratos contra animais - Ligue 198 Polícia Ambiental

Figure 1: Investigation sheet on mistreatment (Mendes, 2020, p. 140)

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TABELA MAUS TRATOS COM CACHORRINHO

NOME: _____

MAU TRATO	QUANTIDADE	TOTAL GERAL	MAU TRATO	QUANTIDADE	TOTAL GERAL

Denuncie os maus tratos contra os animais - Ligue 198 POLÍCIA AMBIENTAL

Figure 2: Table mistreatment of puppies (Mendes, 2020, p. 141)

Task 4: Doing a pictogram (3 hour-class)

The children constructed the graph, Figure 3, using the images cut from the investigation sheet, considering only the images registered in the frequency table of the collected data.

We invited the children to go to the schoolyard, arranged them in a circle, and placed a cardboard representing the graph in the middle, and explained that each child would put on it the images they had cut from the investigation sheets.

Figure 3: Children building the graph (Mendes, 2020, p. 141)

After everyone completed the graph, we explained that we had built a pictogram. Once it got too big, we proposed replacing ten small pieces of paper (chips) with a large one to make the pictogram more visible. The dialogue below shows how it happened:

- Pesquisadora: nossa! nosso gráfico ficou enorme, como vamos fazer para contar?
- Estudante M: contando um por um
- Pesquisadora: mas vão demorar demais, como podemos fazer isso mais rápido?
- Estudante L: escrevendo na tabela

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- Pesquisadora: ah! Sim! Mas antes de escrevermos na tabela, para nosso gráfico ficar mais fácil de enxergar, o que vocês acham de a cada 10 fichinhas dessas pequeninhas, trocarmos por uma grande igual a essa
- Estudantes: como assim?
- Estudante L: escrevendo na tabela
- Pesquisadora: por exemplo, a cada 10 fichinhas pequenas dessa de “crueldade”, nós vamos trocar por essa ficha maior aqui.
- Researcher: wow! our graph is huge, how are we going to count?
- Student M: counting one by one
- Researcher: but it will take too long, how can we do this faster
- Student L: writing on the table
- Researcher: oh! yes, but before we write in the table, to make our chart easier to see, what do you think about every 10 chips of these little ones, we change it for a big one like this one
- Students: I did not understand.
- Student L: writing on the table
- Researcher: for example, for every 10 small tokens of this “cruelty”, we’ll exchange it for this larger one here

In the above dialogue, without conceptual rigor, we worked on the statistical reasoning competency in the specificity presented by Garfield and Gal (1999), that is, reasoning about data representation, which is the understanding of how each type of graph is appropriate to represent a set of data.

This Investigation Context provided students with an initial development of skills necessary for their growth as citizens, in the construction of democracy and citizenship in the search for equity and social justice, which, according to Gerardo (2008), implies looking at the around us and knowing how to interpret what we saw, using a powerful tool – knowledge.

Final considerations

With the development of the tasks of this investigation context, it was possible to go through the four phases of the statistical method: the first phase, which includes the survey of the problem, the second phase comprising data collection, and the third phase of the statistical method select the appropriate graph and numerical methods for data analysis. We explored subjects such as data organisation and representation, as cited in GAISE (Bargagliotti et al., 2007).

The investigation questions started with the researcher and as the children developed new knowledge, they began to elaborate questions and make generalizations, expanding the research universe. The GAISE report (Bargagliotti et al., 2007) points out that planning a study and formulating questions for data collection are tasks that significantly contribute to the development of critical statistical analysis.

The data production was facilitated through questions to the children: for example, “What theme will be researched?”; “How do you search for data?”; “What will be part of the research?”; “How this data will be collected and tabulated?”; “How to present and interpret them?”.

In the course of carrying out the tasks in this Research Context, we observed that the children developed skills to: choose the topic to be investigated (task 1); collect data through the investigation list (task 2); tabulate the data and organize them (task 3); build representations for your data in the pictogram chart (task 4). The results analyzed show that through the tasks of the Research Context, the children showed initial manifestations of statistical skills.

We observe that statistical literacy is present when children are able to understand some statistical terminology and when reading textual information, graphs and tables. During the execution of tasks 2 and 3, we observed that when we handed the children the table and the investigation list, they were already familiar with those terms and already knew how to perform data collection by themselves. With this, we realised that statistical literacy competence was already in development, since they demonstrated an understanding of the statistical terminologies (Garfield, 2002).

In dialogue with the children about the construction of the pictogram (task 4), it was possible to reason about the data. Initially and simply the children worked their reasoning statistical, since “reasoning about data representation, which addresses understanding how the graphs can be modified to represent the data better” (Campos, 2017, p. 98).

Although this investigation context did not approach statistical thinking competence, we can observe that this competence existed, even if implicitly, as by encouraging children to think of a way to collect data (task 2), we prompted them to find an action strategy, which, according to Wodewotzki and Jacobini (2009), pervades statistical thinking.

Thus, we can affirm that 6-year-olds can develop, even initially, statistical competencies such as literacy, statistical reasoning, and statistical thinking when conducting a statistical investigation.

When developing the tasks presented in the investigation context, we observed that they provided for aspects that went beyond statistics education, such as moments when we used resources to open discussions on the topic of animal cruelty, with videos and discussions with children. In this environment, they had space to speak, discuss, expand their communication skills, and dialogue on the theme chosen and the phases of the statistical investigation. The conception of Statistical Education that we assume is directed towards social action, as, “valuing attitudes aimed at social praxis, students engage with the community, transforming classroom reflections into action.” (Campos et al., 2011, p. 12).

The social interactions enhanced by research are of fundamental importance for the construction of a reflective and critical citizen, they are: carrying out a Statistical Investigation (collecting, organizing, analyzing and presenting data); know and recognize the social use of numbers; express their ideas about the mistreatment of Pets topics discussed

in the conversation circles and in the activities; working in groups collaboratively; live with colleagues respecting the individual differences of each one.

It is important to emphasise that for this we must propose tasks that address themes of the children's interests, that are planned based on curriculum guidelines aimed at teaching statistics and that, during its development, the children are made protagonists of the process, which may enable them, as stated by Lopes (2004), to experience its entirety from conception to data analysis.

We emphasise that the aim was to develop a study that would enable children to experience a researchers' role in the statistical process, since they come to school full of curiosity and questions. Thus, we should motivate them, encourage existing curiosities, and provoke others so that the process/cycle/phase of a statistical investigation develops. Here is our contribution to reflection on the development of statistical skills and their role in the formation of critical citizens.

References

- Alro, H., & Skovsmose, O. (2010). *Diálogo e aprendizagem em educação matemática*. Belo Horizonte: Autêntica.
- Bargagliotti, A., Franklin, C., Arnold, P., Gould, R., Johnson, S., Perez, L., Spangler, D. A. (2007). *Pre-K-12 guidelines for assessment and instruction in statistics education II (GAISE II): A framework for statistics and data science education*. Alexandria: American Statistical Association.
- Borba, M. C., & Skovsmose, O. (2001). A ideologia da certeza em educação matemática. In O. Skovsmose (Ed.), *Educação matemática crítica: A questão da democracia* (pp. 127–148). Campinas: Papirus.
- Brasil, Ministério da Educação. (2017). *Base nacional comum curricular*. Brasília: MEC.
- Campos, C. R., Wodewotzki, M. L. L., & Jacobini, O. R. (2011). *Educação estatística: Teoria e prática em ambiente de modelagem matemática*. Belo Horizonte: Autêntica Editora.
- Campos, S. G V. B. (2017). *Sentido de número e estatística: Uma investigação com crianças do 1º Ano do Ciclo de Alfabetização* [Doctoral dissertation, Universidade Estadual Paulista Júlio de Mesquita Filho].
- Chance, B. L. (2002). Components of statistical thinking and implications for instruction and assessment. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 10(3). www.amstat.org/publications/jse/v10n3/chance.html
- Delmas, R. C. (2002). Statistical literacy, reasoning and thinking: A commentary. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 10(3). www.amstat.org/publications/jse
- Dias, E. C. (2000). *A tutela jurídica dos animais*. Belo Horizonte: Mandamentos
- Frankenstein, M. (1987). Critical mathematics education: An application of Paulo Freire's epistemology. In I. Shor (Ed.) *Freire for the classroom* (pp. 180–210). London: Heinemann.
- Gal, I. & Garfield, J. (1997). *The assessment challenge in statistics education*. Amsterdã: IOS Press.
- Garfield, J. (1998). The statistical reasoning assessment: Development and validation of a research tool. In L. P. Mendoza (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Teaching Statistics* (pp. 781–786). Voorburg, Netherlands: International Statistical Institute.
- Guimarães, G. L. (2019). Educação estatística no ensino fundamental: Interfaces entre pesquisas e sala de aula. Presentation at Anais XIII Encontro Nacional de Educação Matemática, Cuiabá.

- Lopes, C. A. E. (2004). Literacia estatística e INAF 2002. In M. C. Fonseca (Ed.). *Letramento no Brasil: Habilidades matemáticas* (pp. 85–97). São Paulo: Global.
- Mendes, V. C. (2020). *Interfaces entre investigação e competências estatísticas: um estudo com crianças do 1º ano do Ensino Fundamental* [Master's thesis, Universidade de Uberaba].
- Rumsey, D. J. (2002). Statistical literacy as a goal for introductory statistics course. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 10(3). www.amstat.org/publications/jse/v10n3/chance.html
- Wodewotzki, M. L. L., & Jacobini, O. R. (2009). *O ensino de estatística no contexto da educação matemática*. In M. A. V. Bicudo & M. C. Borba (Eds.), *Educação matemática: Pesquisa em movimento* (p. 232–249). São Paulo: Cortez.